

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EXTENDED MEANINGS OF TOUCH IN ENGLISH AND BULGARIAN²

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Abstract

The paper presents a comparative study of the perception verb taste with the aim to examine its semantic associations and answer the question what it means to taste in English and Bulgarian in different situations. It aims to discuss the conceptual metaphors underlying the metaphorical expressions related to the English verb of perception “taste” and present what kind of cognitive processes are involved when it is used in various contexts in English and Bulgarian.

Keywords: perception verbs, extended meanings, touch

Introduction

The paper is part of a more detailed study focused on perception verbs and their semantic extensions in English and Bulgarian. It is based on the framework of cognitive semantics, namely, the Conceptual Metaphor Theory for data analysis (Lakoff & Johnson, 2003), which considers metaphor as “understanding and experiencing one kind of thing in terms of another” (ibid., p. 5). It aims to discuss the conceptual metaphors underlying the metaphorical expressions related to the English verb of perception “taste” and present what kind of cognitive processes are involved when it is used in various contexts in English and Bulgarian. Therefore, the descriptions and analyses in this study are usage-based and organized according to the contexts in which the verb appears.

Material and methods

The examples are drawn from two main corpora – the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA), using the free, online version (<https://corpus.byu.edu/coca/>) and the Bulgarian National Corpus (BNC) (<http://dcl.bas.bg/bulnc/en/>). The meanings are grouped in accordance with the purposes of the research and include a set of the most common prototypical and metaphorical uses of the perception verb “taste” in English and Bulgarian.

Our physical experience forms our concepts. According to cognitive linguistics, the concepts we gain through our repeated direct physical experiences contribute to forming abstract conceptual structures. Lakoff (1987) points out that “Abstract conceptual structures are indirectly meaningful; they are understood because of their systematic relationship to directly meaningful structures” (ibid., p. 268). We are therefore capable of interpreting and even forming non-realistic concepts, supported by our direct physical experiences.

Discussion

While vision is considered the most distant and objective sense, taste appears to be the most intuitive and personal sense, which is associated by cognitive linguists with our “internal self” and personal preference (Sweetser 1991, p. 43). Unlike the other senses,

taste is considered the most varying one as physical taste can differ immensely for individuals, even more than touch. It would therefore seem appropriate to link our individual likes and dislikes to the sense of physical taste (Sweetser 1991).

Allan (2008, p. 49) links this sense to individual preferences as only the person who is performing the action is involved in the task of deciding what to taste, an action that one has great control over. Unlike the sense of vision, where one gathers information from a distance, taste is considered to be the sense which requires closeness, what is more, physical contact is necessary. A person must try an object in order to taste it and consequently gather any information regarding a particular object. Similar to touch, this sense is not a reliable source for information, since tasting every item can be both unsuitable socially and dangerous for the individual (Allan, 2008, p. 49). Allan furthermore claims it to be fairly unproductive, as the taste of objects does not give us the necessary information (ibid., p. 49).

Unlike the smell sense, which is mostly related to negative sensation, that of taste is considered to have a positive meaning by default (Allan, 2008). The expression to have taste suggests that one has “a good taste” (ibid., p. 49). Viberg (2008) supports this view, making reference to Swedish, where the default understanding of “taste” is positive (ibid., p. 158). Bulgarian resembles English, as phrases such as “има вкус към/ за” have positive connotations.

Literal meanings

The English verb “taste” and the Bulgarian verbs “вкуся” and “опитвам” are used to identify the lexical meanings of “taste” connected with physical perception presented in the following two patterns:

Pattern 1: S [inanim.] + taste + of/ like + O [inanim.]

Meaning: An inanimate subject has a particular flavour

1. His lips tasted of day-long black coffee.
2. It didn't taste like cheese.
3. Кафето имаше вкус на карамфил и горчиви бадеми.

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Analyzing the corpus lines, it becomes clear that the verb describes a particular quality that can be distinguished by physically trying something. It is important to note that, in all of the corpus lines the perceiver is fully omitted.

Pattern 2: S [anim.] + taste + O [inanim.]

Meaning: An animate subject eats/ drinks something

The examples below illustrate the prototypical meaning of “taste” as an activity verb.

4. Astorre was eating lustily. He had never tasted anything so delicious as this grilled lamb.

5. We first tasted the wine when we sat down at 7 p.m.

6. Беше първото от трите Малъовишки езера и ние опитахме вкуса на бистрата вода.

7. Тогава домакинят е трябвало да опита храната първи, за да я обяви за безопасна пред гостите си.

The use of “taste” in the examples above naturally bears the meaning of actual gustatory perception. In both English and Bulgarian the verb refers to a physical activity that ranges from testing the flavour of the object in (5) ~ (7), which lasts for a second to eating/ consuming food in (4), which is a longer process. This shift in the meaning is strongly dependent on the context in which the verb appears.

Metaphorical meanings

- Experience

The metaphors associated with the sense of taste are explored in the following patterns:

Pattern 3: S [anim.] + taste + O [abstr.]

Meaning: an animate subject experiences a particular feeling

Consider the following corpus lines:

8. Taste the relish to be found in competition.

9. Yes, there I tasted life.

10. За тези 11 години вкусихме от всичко – имаше успехи, имаше и разочарования.

11. Но какъв е смисълът на живота без любовта? Без да си вкусил от сладостта и горчивината й?

Although in the Bulgarian translation of (8) it could be argued that this sentence could also mean “enjoy”, in (11) where love has a bitter taste, this interpretation is not possible. Similarly, the meaning of the verb in (10) is not limited only to experiencing something good as it is linked to positive and negative emotions,

in this case the enjoyment of success but also disappointments. Tasting life in (9) is shifted to “experience”, as life cannot offer only positive feelings.

- to experience something for a short time

The metaphor EXPERIENCE SOMETHING FOR A SHORT TIME requires special attention. Despite overlapping with the previous one (EXPERIENCE), it is still distinctive enough to require a separate category. It is present in both languages under examination. Consider the following examples:

12. Just when he was entering the springtime of life his best life was over... he had tasted freedom only to lose it.

13. Вкусих малко от живота на богатшите.

The corpus lines clearly show that the focus here is on the brevity of emotions. This meaning is implied by the background information where “tasting” is followed by the phrases “only to lose it” in (12) and “a little” in (13).

- Enjoy

Pattern 4: S [anim.] + taste + O [abstr.]

Meaning: an animate subject enjoys something

Although Pattern 4 is the same in grammatical structure as Pattern 3, its semantic content is different from that of “taste” in the meaning of “experience” in that it focuses not only on experiential interpretation but on the positive side of experiencing something. The metaphor ENJOYING IS TASTING is illustrated in the following examples:

14. She was tired of London. She had seen all that it had to offer and tasted every one of its delights, many times.

15. Вкуси карнавала!

16. Вкуси прелестите на пролетта!

17. I tasted African culture with the Ethiopian children and am eager for more!

Analyzing the corpus lines above it becomes clear that the meaning of the verb “taste” refers to enjoyment and thus the corpus lines exemplify the specific metaphor EXPERIENCING/ WITNESSING PLEASANT EVENTS IS TASTING. Tasting the delights that the city has to offer in (14), or the carnival in (15) involves not only the idea of participation but rather the feeling of enjoyment. The same is the meaning of the verb in (16) where the verb “вкуся” (“taste”) is followed by a lexical item that has positive connotations (the delights of the spring). In (17) tasting culture arises pleasant emotions and the meaning “experience something pleasant” is profiled by the feeling of eagerness to experience more.

Table 1

summarizes the analysed patterns.

Pattern	Meaning
Pattern 1: S [inanim.] + taste + of/ like + O [inanim.]	Meaning: An inanimate subject has a particular flavour
Pattern 2: S [anim.] + taste + O [inanim.]	Meaning: An animate subject eats/ drinks something
Pattern 3: S [anim.] + taste + O [abstr.]	Meaning: An animate subject experiences a particular feeling
Pattern 4: S [anim.] + taste + O [abstr.]	Meaning: An animate subject enjoys something

Table 1: Patterns of “taste”

Conclusion

The result of the metaphorical comparison between English and Bulgarian demonstrates a noticeable link between abstract and physical meanings of the perception verb “taste”. Although there is no close relation between the two languages, the high number of analogous metaphorical meanings suggests that the similar-

ity is not a coincidence, which supports Sweetser’s theory of a systematic, semantic development within perception verbs. The analysis clearly shows that the abstract meanings having developed early within the Indo-European language family are also present in different branches of the Indo-European languages. That development is evident in the two languages under investigation, as the comparison confirmed.

Fig 1: Extended meanings of “taste” in English and Bulgarian

The analysis of the verb “taste” in both languages clearly shows that contexts are of main importance when interpreting the meanings conveyed by lexical items. This view of lexical meanings is also useful for pedagogical purposes. It is undoubtedly more effective if the meanings of words and expressions of a second language are learnt not only through one-to-one correspondence with the words and expressions of one’s native language, but also through understanding the concepts behind lexical units. This approach is essential in building up and expanding students’ lexical knowledge in the second language, since words and expressions learned as groups of concepts would allow them to better understand the different usages of their meanings. What is more, this approach has proven to be more reliable than memorizing dictionary entries.

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